

Concept of Authority in Muslim Political Thought of Medieval India: A Comparative Study of Zia-ud-Din Barani and Abul Fazal

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Abstract

Muslim political thought in India during the medieval period presents a rich source of ideas and principles that shaped governance in India. The Delhi Sultanate, established in the early 13th century, was the first of the major Muslim states in India that set foundational models in administration, law, and intercultural and inter-religious relations. The Mughal Empire, which succeeded the Delhi Sultanate in the 16th century, was marked by a more advanced and sophisticated administration, depicting strong Persian influences and also having an impact on Islamic political ideals. The main elements of Muslim political thought during this era included the concept of a divine right to rule. Whether the rulers expressed themselves as caliphs or not or whether they allied themselves with the Muslim Caliphate at that time is an interesting matter to be looked at. The principles adopted by both the Sultans and Mughals to justify their rule in India with multiple religions and multiple ethnicities within Muslims all struggling for influence and power in the court and the king's attempt to establish his authority makes this a valuable study having something to learn for the current political order and governance. The article adopts a comparative approach and takes Zia-ud-Din Barani from the Sultanate period and Abul Fazal from the Mughal Empire and attempts to explore their ideas about political authority. It looks into the questions of how and why political authority has been justified by these two political thinkers and what role they assign to the masses and common people in the establishment of that authority.

Keywords: Political Authority, Zia-ud-Din Barani, Abul Fazal, Delhi Sultanate, Mughal Empire, Muslim Political Thought

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INTRODUCTION

Political thought refers to the ideas, philosophies, and beliefs that shape our understanding of politics, government, and the role of the state in society. It encompasses various theories, concepts, and ideologies that have evolved over time, influencing political discourse, decision-making, and action. Political thought addresses questions such as: What is the purpose of government? What is the nature of power and authority? How should society be organized? What are the rights and responsibilities of citizens? How should conflicts be resolved?¹ This paper will focus on the nature of power and authority and the question of sovereignty during the medieval era of India.

The research explores the political thought or ideas of the two leading thinkers and historians of medieval India; Ziauddin Barani and Abul Fazl. The comparative study emphasizes exploring the works done on the political thought of these two philosophers. For Barani English translation of his monumental work, *Fatawa-i-Jahandari* is the main source of this research and for the discussion on Abul Fazl's political thought English translations of *Ain I Akbari* and *Akbarnama* have been used. *Religious and Intellectual History of the Muslims in Akbar's Reign, with Special Reference to Abu'l Fazl*, a book by, Saiyid Athar Abbas Rizvi has also been consulted. Other important works have also been used to discern and comprehend the political thought of Barani and Abul Fazl.

Ziauddin Barani (b1283-1359d) was an important political thinker during the Delhi Sultanate. He lived through the reigns of rulers like Alauddin Khilji, Muhammad Bin Tughlaq, and Feroz Tughlaq. Barani is considered one of the most important historians and political thinkers of Medieval India. His books give us valuable information about the political structure of the sultans of Delhi. Barani is very important not just for recording the past but also for his ideas about kingship, its purpose, and duties. He introduced the idea of being practical in politics.² His work, *Fatawa-i-Jahandari*, offers advice to Muslim rulers and is a classic on governance, comparable to Kautilya's *Arthashastra* and Machiavelli's *The Prince*. Barani has been criticized as a fundamentalist, and bigoted compared to more liberal thinker Abul Fazl by renowned historian Mohammad Habib.³ His work, *Tarikh-i-Feroze Shahi*, is a reliable source of history from the later period of Ghiasuddin Balban to the initial time of Feroze Shah Tughluq. The book was also dedicated to Feroz Shah. In addition to recounting historical events, Barani addresses the political issues of Muslims. He addresses the important question of how to implement Islamic *shariah* laws in the new state of the Muslims of India. However, the focus of the book is on writing history. He has given his political ideas in his other work, *Fatawa-i-Jahandari*. *Fatawa-i-Jahandari*, offers advice to Sultans and Kings, using Sultan Mahmud of Ghazna, as the ideal ruler, to illustrate how can a good empire be established by employing Islamic *Shariah*.⁴ Barani provides a way to judge

¹ For details on the concept and history of Political Thought see Mont J. Harmon, *Political Thought: From Plato to the Present*, Antony Black, *The History of Islamic Political Thought: From the Prophet to the Present*, Bertrand Russell, *History of Western Philosophy*, Muhammad Asad, *The Principles of State and Government in Islam*, Erwin I. J. Rosenthal, *Political Thought in Medieval Islam: An Introductory Outline*, Patricia Crone, *Medieval Islamic Political Thought*, Gerhard Bowering, ed., *Islamic Political Thought: An Introduction*

² Vasileios Syros. "State Failure and Successful Leadership in Medieval India." *Studies in History*, 37 (2021): 7 - 25. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02576430211001961>.

³ Raziuddin Aqil, *The Muslim Question: Understanding Islam and Indian History* (Random House Publishers India Pvt. Limited, 2017), 66.

⁴ Sheikh Mohamad Ikram, *History of Muslim Civilization in India and Pakistan: A Political and Cultural History* (Institute of Islamic Culture, 1989), 161.

the importance of social actions. His perspective and reason for studying history are focused on the interests of the ruling class.⁵ Barani's political philosophy centers on the king's role. He offers various advice to the king on how to implement his ideas.

For Barani, the king is crucial and should have control over all state matters. He believes that the king must apply Islamic *Shariah* in all aspects of life fairly and effectively. Barani's main goal is the implementation of Islamic *Shariah*. He addresses various issues regarding this, some of which can be criticized and some praised. In Barani's mind, Islamic law is not just strict rules. It is about making good things win over bad things. Bad stuff will always be around. The king should pick good, honest people to run the government, army, spies, and judges. In this way, good people can fight the bad people. This fight between good and bad will never really end until judgment day.⁶

Barani's political work is a valuable treatise, comparable to Nizamul Mulk Tusi's *Siyasat Nama* Fakhr-i-Mudabbir's *Adabul-Harb* and Syed Ali Hamdani's *Zakhiratul-Muluk*. Barani's work contains more detailed information.⁷ Sultan Mahmud, Barani's ideal king, or his successors should not live like common people. If they did, the people would not respect them or accept their rule. Therefore, Barani's suggestion to the ruler is to live with grandeur and awe. This is important as the honor and integrity of Islam are closely connected to the king's respected image.

The king's character should align with Islamic ideals. He should be honest, brave, and farsighted. Barani asserts that a good king cannot have a bad character. If the ruler has a poor character, people will see him as an agent of evil.⁸ The king should sincerely follow Islamic *Shariah* in all aspects of governance. While formulating state policies ruler should also follow the advice from his ministers and advisors. He should also set rules for his officers and ministers after consulting knowledgeable and experienced people.⁹ Barani is simultaneously concerned with following the principles of Islam but also looking for able and qualified persons for various vital positions in the state. Barani suggests that the king should be very careful when choosing state officers. He should select sincere, God-fearing, and dedicated individuals. He should avoid appointing people of low birth, bad habits, irreligious nature, and limited vision. If the ruler entrusts his government to nobles with bad character, his downfall and destruction are certain, and will also face punishment from Allah on the day of Resurrection. A good king needs honest and fair advisors to keep the kingdom strong and running smoothly. If the king picks bad advisors, things will get messy and out of control. That is why it is important to choose advisors who are qualified people and follow the teachings of Islam. His focus for the entire state apparatus is centered around following Islamic values. For instance, he states that when selecting nobles, officers, and advisors, the king should

⁵ Irfan Habib, "Barani's Theory of the History of Delhi Sultanate," *ICHR, New Delhi* 7, no. 1–2 (1981–1980): 100, <http://archive.org/details/IrfanHabibBaranisTheoryDelhiSultanate>.

⁶ Vasileios Syros, "Indian Emergencies: Barani's Fatāwā-I Jahāndārī, the Diseases of the Body Politic, and Machiavelli's 'Accidenti,'" *Philosophy East and West* 62, no. 4 (2012): 548–49.

⁷ Riaz Ahmad, "Political Philosophy of Zia-Ud-Din Barani," *Pakistan Journal of History & Culture* Vol.25/1 (2004): 35–36.

⁸ M. Athar Ali, "Theories of Sovereignty in Islamic Thought in India," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 43 (1982): 815–16.

⁹ Ahmad, "Political Philosophy of Zia-Ud-Din Barani." 37.

consider the following qualities. 1) love for Islamic ideals. 2) sincerity and of noble birth. This Barani explains in advice six in *Fatawa-i-Jahandari*.¹⁰

For greater efficiency and effective rule, the king should also have a policy of proper promotions for all the state officials.¹¹ Muslims should always be given preference over all the Hindus and non-Muslims in all the important positions. Barani's contemporary Amir Khusrau has more praise and accommodating inclusive views towards Hindus and other non-Muslims of India.¹² Rulers should not focus solely on building their empire and collecting taxes for their enjoyment, as Hindu Rajas do. Instead, Muslim kings and sultans should work hard to promote Islam and eliminate un-Islamic practices in their territories. Doing this will protect Islamic laws and ensure the honor of Muslims, allowing them to prevail over evil forces. If Muslim kings permit un-Islamic practices to continue and only concentrate on collecting taxes, they won't achieve Islamic goals. This neglect will damage the value of Islamic principles and the honor of Muslims. It will also prevent Muslim dominance over all non-Muslims.¹³

Barani supports the King's absolute authority and is strongly opposed to any revolt or trouble in any part of the empire. He says that revolt should be firmly crushed immediately.¹⁴ King should have a proper plan to solve problems otherwise the situation will get out of control. When people know that the king has a strong spy network and their secret plans and talks are reported to him, they will be scared to meet secretly or make any kind of conspiracies.¹⁵ Sultan Mahmud's example is given by Barani who while selecting his intelligence officers was very cautious.¹⁶ He gave them the best salaries, great privileges, and positions of honor at various levels of government. These positions were always given to people very close to the Sultan. They acted as the king's agents or messengers. He appointed individuals who were truthful, accurate in reporting, of noble birth, trustworthy, confident, inquisitive, and of high integrity.¹⁷

Barani argues that a key requirement for a good king to establish his authority and maintain sovereignty is maintaining an efficient and disciplined army. Barani offers the following advice number seven:

1. The king should always take care of his loyal workers as his entire rule depends on them.
2. He should spend a lot of money to hire and support his workers. For example, he should be willing to pay a lot to get dedicated soldiers. The army should have everything they need

¹⁰ Mohammad Habib and Afsar Umar Salim Khan, *The Political Theory of the Delhi Sultanate: (Including a Translation of Ziauddin Barani's Fatawa-i Jahandari, Circa, 1358-9 A.D.)* (Kitab Mahal, 1961), 19.

¹¹ Habib and Khan, 20.

¹² Syed Hasan Askari, *Ameer Khusrau As A Historian* (Patna: Khuda Bakhsh Oriental Public Library, 1988), 19–22, <https://www.rekhta.org/ebooks/detail/ameer-khusrau-as-a-historian-syed-hasan-askari-ebooks>.

¹³ Habib and Khan, *The Political Theory of the Delhi Sultanate*, 53–53.

¹⁴ Syros, "Indian Emergencies," 555.

¹⁵ Habib and Khan, *The Political Theory of the Delhi Sultanate*, 30–32.

¹⁶ P. Hardy, "Unity and Variety in Indo-Islamic and Perso-Islamic Civilization: Some Ethical and Political Ideas of Ḍiyā' al-Dīn Baranī of Delhi, of al-Ghazālī and of Naṣīr al-Dīn Tūsī Compared," *Iran* 16 (1978): 129–30, <https://doi.org/10.2307/4299652>.

¹⁷ Ahmad, "Political Philosophy of Zia-Ud-Din Barani." 45.

so that the soldiers and other workers do not have to worry about anything else. The king and his kingdom will be better served by them.¹⁸

In Advice number ten he discusses that the king cannot maintain a large army and efficient administration unless he ensures that people's economic needs are met affordably. Therefore, a king should make proper price control mechanisms for the markets.¹⁹ To elevate the people's economic life, the king must work hard with sincerity. This depicts the economic understanding of Barani for a successful sovereign state. Barani has laid special emphasis on the significance of consultation for the king. The king must seek advice from experts in different fields to achieve important goals. The advice should benefit both the ruler and the masses equally. The ruler should consider both the negative and positive aspects of every action.²⁰ The advice should not endanger the religion. It should bring immediate benefits and long-term positive effects. It should lead to good outcomes, not bad ones. It should turn enemies into friends.²¹ This according to Barani is vital for a king to establish control and authority over his empire. Barani considered consultation part of the Islamic principles of good governance and just rule.

Barani emphasizes that an efficient justice system is a crucial part of Islam. There can be no true practice of Islam without a proper justice system. Justice helps create balance in human society. If there is no justice, Islamic principles cannot thrive in society. Establishing justice is very important for the king because people cannot focus on serving Allah unless criminals are strictly punished.²² In Advice fourteen, Barani says the king should make good policies, rules, and regulations to create a strong government. These policies should follow Islamic *Shariah* and help differentiate right from wrong.²³ The policies should help both now and in the future. If they do not help both the people and the king, they are not good laws and policies.

The advice fifteen explains that after making these laws, the king and his administrators should strictly enforce them. The laws and rules should be created with advice from Ulama, scholars, and Islamic thinkers, and should consider the local situation. Sultan Mahmud's example should be followed by all the rulers of India. The state will be secured by following those rules. Sultan Mahmud took about two years to make these rules with help from intellectuals like Ahmad Hasan, Ali Abu Sehl, and Asfar Aini. During his 36-year rule, Mahmud strictly enforced these rules, making sure his administration was strong and stable.²⁴ To truly serve the interests of Islam in a corrupt time, Barani says that kings should be different from their people by being powerful, grand, dignified, and strict. People who do not fear God's word should be made to fear the king's power. However, for those who are naturally good, obedient, and faithful, the king should be kind, caring, and gentle.²⁵

¹⁸ Habib and Khan, *The Political Theory of the Delhi Sultanate*, 21–26.

¹⁹ Padmesh Pathak, "Ziyauddin Barani's Theory of Price Control—a Critical Estimate," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 45 (1984): 297–98.

²⁰ Hardy, "Unity and Variety in Indo-Islamic and Perso-Islamic Civilization," 132.

²¹ Habib and Khan, *The Political Theory of the Delhi Sultanate*, 8–10.

²² Ahmad, "Political Philosophy of Zia-Ud-Din Barani," 57–58.

²³ Habib and Khan, *The Political Theory of the Delhi Sultanate*, 58–60.

²⁴ Habib and Khan, 71–72.

²⁵ P. Hardy, "The 'Oratio Recta' of Barani's 'Ta'rikh-i-Firuz Shāhī'—Fact or Fiction?" *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London* 20, no. 1/3 (1957): 319.

Barani's writing is a comprehensive one that in essence encapsulates all important dimensions of statecraft. He explains how a king should choose honest and dedicated officials, follow Islamic laws, and make fair policies. These policies should help both the present and future and be made with advice from knowledgeable people. Barani also says that strict enforcement of these laws is crucial for a strong government. He highlights the example of Sultan Mahmud, who created and enforced effective rules with the help of experts, ensuring a stable administration. Barani explains that the king's sovereignty should remain unaffected by anybody.²⁶ In the exercise of power and decision-making, he should not accept any kind of pressure from anyone. The king's *harem* should also not influence state matters. This independence is crucial because individuals with evil intentions may try to control the king and influence his policies. Qurashi has made a pertinent distinction between the legal and real sovereign during medieval India. The legal sovereign during the medieval Islamic state was the *Shariah* and the real sovereign was the sultan.²⁷

Barani gives the example of Qabad, Nausherwan's father, who let Mazdik, a bad and untrustworthy person, run the government. This caused chaos in the empire.²⁸ Barani tried to solve the conflict between being a king and following Islam by saying that the qualities of a good king are like the qualities of God. He also stressed the importance of having secular (non-religious) laws in addition to religious laws. This was another way to resolve the conflict between religion and practical politics. These state laws can be traditional or new, created by the king with advice from wise advisors to adapt to changing times and situations.²⁹ Zia Barani's political philosophy focuses on the importance of justice, good governance, and adherence to Islamic principles. He believes that rulers should appoint honest, God-fearing officials and create fair policies based on Islamic *Shariah*. These policies should benefit both the present and future. Barani emphasizes the need for strict enforcement of laws to ensure stability and security. He warns against giving power to corrupt or incompetent individuals, using historical examples to show the negative consequences of such actions. He also has a clear preference for Muslims over non-Muslims for the key posts of the government. For him, the king's sovereignty and authority emanate from Islamic principles. If the ruler is a true believer, he is not only a good ruler but must also be obeyed by all. Overall, Barani's philosophy is about maintaining a just and stable government that upholds Islamic values.

The study of human history reveals quite clearly that change is a constant phenomenon. This change can be seen at both material and ideological levels. The following discussion about the political ideas of Abul Fazl during the Mughal empire is a testament to this aspect of changes in political ideas over time. The rule of Akbar the Great, from 1556 to 1605, is a standout period in medieval India's political history. During this time, India's social and political conditions changed significantly, the ideas about government and the philosophy of the state were reconsidered, and the administrative system was reorganized. Shaikh Abul Fazl Aliami (14 January 1551 – 22 August 1602), was the brilliant mind behind many of Akbar's political strategies. He was a key figure of his time, serving a high position in Akbar's court as advisor, chief secretary, official historian,

²⁶ Habib and Khan, *The Political Theory of the Delhi Sultanate*, 169–71.

²⁷ Ishtiaq Husain Qureshi, *The Administration of the Sultanate of Delhi* (Oriental Books Reprint Corporation; exclusively distributed by Munshiram Manoharlal, 1971). 42–43.

²⁸ Irfan Habib, "A Political Theory For The Mughal Empire — A Study Of The Ideas Of Abu'l Fazl," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 59 (1998): 21–22.

²⁹ Antony Black, *The History of Islamic Political Thought: From the Prophet to the Present*, 1st edition (New York: Routledge, 2001), 166–67.

legislator, and head of the Diwani Department.³⁰ By the age of fifteen, Abul Fazl had thoroughly studied both rational and traditional sciences. His studies were both broad and deep, earning him significant recognition in the academic world.³¹

When Abul Fazl was 23 years old, his older brother Abu'l Faizi introduced him to Emperor Akbar's court. Later, Faizi would become the court's main poet. Abul Fazl wrote a book that has two main parts: the *Akbar Nama* and the *Ain-i-Akbari*. There are two sections of *Akbar Nama*: The first section talks about Akbar's family history. The second section gives a comprehensive, year-by-year account of Akbar's rule. Third part of the book is *Ain-i-Akbari*. It contains Abul Fazl's ideas about politics and government. It uniquely details the administrative system and management of various government departments in a vast empire. The *Ain-i-Akbari* is a remarkable book. It explains the history of Emperor Akbar with detailed records about many important things like revenue, the royal household, the treasury, military rules, and more. It includes a list of Indian places and a collection of the emperor's sayings and teachings. No other book gives such a detailed and lively picture of India at that time. It covers customs, traditions, manners, recipes, and religious changes. The book is written in the grand style of a royal journal.³² Abul Fazl, like most medieval thinkers, believes that hierarchy is a natural part of society. He thinks all societies are divided into groups that can be ranked. However, in Abul Fazl's *Ain-i Akbari*, there are many different kinds of hierarchies based on profession, skill, and natural traits.³³

Abul Fazl categorizes religious beliefs into four groups based on their belief in the soul's post-death state, with one group promoting resurrection. Another group believes in the soul moving to a new body (transmigration). A third group thinks the soul is reborn in the same body after some time. The fourth group, which he thinks is wrong, believes the human body is like grass. He also describes different beliefs people have towards life and the afterlife: Some are happy thinking they will go to heaven, while others fear going to hell. Some hope to see the divine, even if it seems unlikely, while others believe in the soul moving to a new body. Another group tries to be better people to gain divine favor. Some people focus only on the present, not caring about the future, and many just seek physical comfort.³⁴

Abul Fazl himself does not belong to any of these groups. He believes that fear of hell prevents sincere prayer. He prays for true knowledge and guidance on the right path. He reflects on Sufi's ideas of the heaven and the hell, noting that most people may have different views on what they look like, but they agree on their true essence. He asks God to remove thoughts of heaven and hell from his mind, seeing them as distractions.³⁵ Abul Fazl wants to stay committed to the idea of *Wahdat al-Wujud*, Unity of Being. This concept was taught by Ibn 'Arabi and many of his Sufi followers. The idea means understanding that we are already united with the ultimate Reality, which is both One and All. However, Abul Fazl also follows another idea called *Wajib al-Wujud*

³⁰ Abul Fazl Usmani, "Political Ideas of Shaikh Abul Fazl Allami (1556—1602)," *The Indian Journal of Political Science* 24, no. 3 (1963): 264.

³¹ H. Blochmann, *Ain-i-Akbari Vol. 4*, 1873, <http://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.32526>. ii.

³² S. M. Jaffar, *The Mughal Empire, from Bābar to Aurangzeb* (Ess Publications, 1936), 163.

³³ Najaf Haider, "Money and Social Inequality: The Views of Abul Fazl," *Studies in People's History* 3 (May 5, 2016): 1, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2348448916636694>.

³⁴ Saiyid Athar Abbas Rizvi, *Religious and Intellectual History of the Muslims in Akbar's Reign, with Special Reference to Abu'l Fazl, 1556-1605* (Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers, 1975), 342.

³⁵ Rizvi, 342.

(Necessary Being) from the *Ishraqis*. This idea focuses on the existence of a necessary and ultimate being.³⁶

Abul Fazl consistently believes that everything from God is good and applies this to his interactions with others. He believes there are only two ways to treat people: the least we can do is to be peaceful with everyone, and the best is to be loving towards everyone. This idea comes from the Sufi belief that people are made in the image of God. This means that, according to Sufism, everyone reflects God's qualities and deserves respect and love. For Abul Fazl, a good life involves more than just prayer and invocation; it requires universal harmony (*sulh-i kul*) and serving all of humanity, regardless of religious or sectarian differences. "Universal harmony" gets rid of conflict and selfishness and is the best cure for hatred. Abul Fazl admits that it is hard to achieve because it means controlling our basic instincts and desires, which often lead us to follow our passions instead of living harmoniously.³⁷

The defeat of the *Ulama* in religious debates at the 'House of Worship' established Abul Fazl's dominance in state affairs. This enabled him to convince the emperor that the people should see the king as both their temporal and spiritual leader. This concept shaped the central idea of Abul Fazl's political philosophy and marked a revolutionary change in Mughal state theory. It challenged the Quranic law, which was supposed to be above everything else and binding on the king as well. This caused an uproar. The *Ulama* resisted, but Abul Fazl's control was so strong that they had no choice but to accept their defeat.³⁸ Abul Fazl's political ideas are closely connected to his religious beliefs about God and aim to affirm people's right to a well-ordered life and the pursuit of goodness and happiness. His views support the Iranian theory of kingship, which is also embraced by those who defend the Sultanate, believing that faith and kingship are interdependent.³⁹ Abul Fazl has not given sources of his political thought but we can say that it is based on several groups of works:

"Mirrors for Princes, including Firdausi's *Shak Nama* and advisory books by Ghazali, Nizamul Mulk Tusi, and their followers. Works by Avicenna and his interpreters such as Nasirud Din Tusi and Jalalud-Din Dauwani. Histories of the Mongols, which elaborate on the concept of the divine origin of imperial power. Ancient Indian political thought was mainly based on the *Dharmashastra* (The Laws of Manu), the *Mahabharata*, and the *Kalila wa Dimna*."⁴⁰

Abul Fazl aimed to support Akbar's policies and goals. He built his ideas on the *Sasanid* belief that true rulers are given a divine light, showing they are chosen by a higher power. This meant he wanted to show that Akbar's rule was justified and blessed by the divine light.⁴¹ Abul Fazl, rather than influencing Akbar, likely absorbed the emperor's idealism and eagerly helped to achieve it. In doing so, he also became Akbar's most reliable and important interpreter.⁴² Abul Fazl did not

³⁶ Rizvi, 345.

³⁷ Rizvi, 351.

³⁸ Usmani, "Political Ideas of Shaikh Abul Fazl Allami (1556—1602)," 267.

³⁹ Rizvi, *Religious and Intellectual History of the Muslims in Akbar's Reign, with Special Reference to Abu'l Fazl, 1556-1605*, 352.

⁴⁰ Rizvi, 352.

⁴¹ H. Beveridge, *The Akbarnama Of Abul Fazl Vol. 1*, 1907, 36–37, <http://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.55648>.

⁴² S. R. Sharma, "Abul Fazl as a Political Thinker," *The Indian Journal of Political Science* 9, no. 1 (1948): 44.

view Akbar as a divine incarnation just like Hindu concept of an avatar, but certainly viewed him as a divine messenger sent to lead humanity out of darkness and chaos. To Abul Fazl, Akbar was the personification of an ideal monarch.⁴³

He adds:

“Royalty is a light emanating from God, and a ray from the sun, the illuminator of the Universe. This light is communicated by God to Kings without the intermediate assistance of anyone. Kingship is a refulgence (*furugh*) from the Incomparable Distributor of justice (God) and a ray from the Sun, the illuminator of the universe, the index of the books of perfection, and the receptacle of all virtues... It is communicated by God to the holy face (of the king) without the intermediate assistance of anyone; and men, in its presence, bend the forehead of praise towards the ground of submission. Again, many excellent qualities flow from the possession of this light.”⁴⁴

Abul Fazl's deep understanding of Muslim and Greek philosophies, acquired through Arabic and Persian translations, was significantly shaped by the local conditions and circumstances of his time. He firmly believes that in the eyes of God, no dignity is higher than royalty. This means he considers kingship to be a position of great honor and importance, sanctioned by divine approval.⁴⁵ Abul Fazl strives to grant his monarch absolute power by attributing supernatural authority to him.⁴⁶ Therefore, he strongly condemns any attempt at revolution. He defines the duties of the king clearly: protecting the lives, property, honor, and religious freedom of his subjects. In return, the king deserves complete obedience. Abul Fazl's king, as a guardian of religion, does not prefer any one faith, showing his secular views. This means the king treats all religions equally and does not show favoritism to any specific one.⁴⁷

He argues against using fear or force as a lasting foundation for political obedience. Fear creates resistance, and force provokes retaliation. For effective governance, willing cooperation and mutual understanding between the government and the governed are essential. Abul Fazl believes it is wise to establish a philosophical basis for cooperation with Akbar's kingship.⁴⁸ To Abul Fazl, kingship serves to fulfill the divine will and is a primary force for the people's welfare and the success of any action. He asserts that royalty is highly esteemed by God and those who are wise benefit from its blessings. According to him, the term "*Padshah*" signifies stability and possession, with the king being the source of both. Abul Fazl argues that without kingship, conflicts would

⁴³ Sharma, 44.

⁴⁴ Rizvi, *Religious and Intellectual History of the Muslims in Akbar's Reign, with Special Reference to Abu'l Fazl, 1556-1605*, 354.

⁴⁵ Rizvi, 354.

⁴⁶ Jos Gommans and Said Reza Huseini, "Neoplatonism and the Pax Mongolica in the Making of Şulh-i Kull. A View from Akbar's Millennial History," *Modern Asian Studies* 56, no. 3 (May 2022): 870–901, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0026749X21000044>.

⁴⁷ Usmani, "Political Ideas of Shaikh Abul Fazl Allami (1556—1602)," 274.

⁴⁸ Usmani, 274.

persist, and selfish ambitions would never cease.⁴⁹ He was also influenced by *Nuqtavis*. They migrated to Mughal India to get protection from persecution in Persia.⁵⁰

A true king, in Abul Fazl's view, seeks to alleviate oppression and promote the common good. Political harmony is achieved through a fair division of ranks and the warmth of unity and concord among the people.⁵¹ Abul Fazl himself was a great patriotic Indian and had praise for his people.⁵² Abul Fazl emphasizes that good rulers address both major and minor issues equally. With the help of God, they shoulder the responsibilities of worldly affairs and the afterlife with resolve and determination. King is merely viewed as a source of solace by common people but wise people know that their spiritual progress also depends on the king, who embodies the divine light of God.⁵³ Each of his actions in governance will then be seen as a form of devotion to God. Abul Fazl deliberately rejects the prevalent Afghan theory that anyone who proves themselves fit can aspire to kingship. Instead, he believes kingship is a divine gift bestowed only upon individuals chosen by God. He draws his arguments from the mythical Mongol origin theory and Hindu philosophy, which emphasize the necessity of supernatural descent for kingship.⁵⁴

Abul Fazl argues that Kingship is a gift from God; it can only be granted when many essential qualities are gathered in an individual. Simply having ancestry, wealth, or support from the masses is not sufficient for such a lofty position.⁵⁵ Abul Fazl followed a two-part plan. First, he strongly emphasized that the Mughal Empire was made up of many different ethnic groups and religions. Second, he portrayed Akbar as the protector of this diverse mix of people in India.⁵⁶ Abul Fazl's strategy had two main goals. The first was to highlight and affirm the diverse nature of the Mughal Empire, showing it as a place where many cultures and religions coexisted. The second goal was to depict Akbar, the emperor, as someone who safeguarded and valued this diversity, making him a key figure in maintaining harmony among the different groups in the vast empire.

According to Abul Fazl, a true king must fear God, uphold justice, prioritize the people's happiness, understand the spirit of the times, and be kind, vigilant, and patient. He must also prevent sectarian differences from causing strife.⁵⁷ Abul Fazl has a different view from traditional Muslim philosophy, which says that *Sharia* should guide all human actions and society. Instead, he thinks that everything should follow the 'Divine Will.' He believes the king understands this Divine Will best through his intuition and interprets it for everyone. He openly acknowledges that the dual authority of kings and scholars (*Ulama*) is the root cause of all troubles. This indicates his belief in concentrating all authority under the king to avoid conflicts and ensure effective governance. Akbar was given the titles of imam and the mujtahid of his time. These were unusual titles for a king, especially the title of the mujtahid, which meant having the authority to make decisions on

⁴⁹ Usmani, 275.

⁵⁰ A. Azfar Moin, *The Millennial Sovereign: Sacred Kingship and Sainthood in Islam* (Columbia University Press, 2012), 178, <https://doi.org/10.7312/moin16036>.

⁵¹ Usmani, "Political Ideas of Shaikh Abul Fazl Allami (1556—1602)," 277–78.

⁵² M. Athar Ali, "The Evolution of the Perception of India: Akbar and Abu'l Fazl," *Social Scientist* 24, no. 1/3 (1996): 84–85, <https://doi.org/10.2307/3520120>.

⁵³ Usmani, "Political Ideas of Shaikh Abul Fazl Allami (1556—1602)," 275.

⁵⁴ Usmani, 275.

⁵⁵ Rizvi, *Religious and Intellectual History of the Muslims in Akbar's Reign, with Special Reference to Abu'l Fazl, 1556-1605*, 357.

⁵⁶ Munis D. Faruqui, *The Princes of the Mughal Empire, 1504–1719* (Cambridge University Press, 2012), 142.

⁵⁷ Faruqui, 142.

religious matters. This title was usually for top Islamic scholars who could use reasoned judgment (ijtihad) to solve complex legal issues not clearly addressed in religious texts or previous laws. For Akbar, a ruler, to claim the status of mujtahid was a bold move but it was not completely new. There was a similar case with the Abbasid caliph al-Ma'mun (ruling from 813 to 833) in Baghdad, who tried to force leading Muslim jurists to accept him as the top authority on Islamic doctrine and law through an event known as the inquisition (mihna).⁵⁸

Abul Fazl's theory differs from the concept of Khilafat also both in its methods and goals. While Khilafat aims to protect the Muslim faith and society, Abul Fazl's *Padshah* seeks the welfare of all subjects equally, regardless of religion or other differences. Khilafat is fundamentally religious in its perspective, while *Padshahat* takes a primarily secular approach.⁵⁹ The Khalifa serves as the leader of a religious order, whereas the *Padshah* is the leader of a political society. Abul Fazl views obedience as the path of righteousness and rejects rebellion entirely. He argues that with the authority of the empire, some people choose to obey willingly, while others avoid doing wrong because they fear being punished. They are compelled by necessity to choose the path of rectitude. This reflects his belief in the importance of order and adherence to authority for maintaining societal harmony. To justify his predetermined idea of kingship, Abul Fazl elevates his king to a high status and secures his political authority with religious endorsements. Once the king is granted the absolute powers as a divine gift, then there will be no revolt.⁶⁰ He conveniently overlooks any allowance for revolution as per Islamic law.

Abul Fazl takes his theory to its logical conclusion. Similar to Plato's concept of the 'Philosopher King', Abul Fazl envisions that only in an ideal society can the king fulfill his role perfectly. He compares a king to a gardener, stating that just as a gardener tends to his garden by removing weeds and keeping the flower beds in order, a king must similarly protect his subjects from harm and maintain order, preventing any external disturbances. This analogy underscores Abul Fazl's belief in the king's responsibility to ensure societal harmony and well-being.⁶¹ Abul Fazl follows Plato's concept that a philosopher king should strive to be as much like God as possible, which means being righteous, holy, and wise. In simpler terms, they believe that the best ruler strives for moral and intellectual excellence, akin to divine qualities of goodness and wisdom.⁶²

Farabi discusses happiness and perfection, solely for the Muslims. Abul Fazl extends his concern to all people. His ideal ruler is not considered perfect simply by adhering to Islamic laws. Instead, he embodies the concept of the Perfect Man (*Insan-i Kamil*), possessing a greater capacity to receive divine enlightenment than anyone else.⁶³ This ruler understands the connection between spiritual and worldly matters and effectively balances both aspects. Abul Fazl respects the *Sharia*, but he believes that if strictly adhering to it would harm the welfare and happiness of his subjects, the ruler has the liberty to set it aside. In simpler terms, Abul Fazl's ideal ruler prioritizes the well-

⁵⁸ Moin, *The Millennial Sovereign*, 153.

⁵⁹ Usmani, "Political Ideas of Shaikh Abul Fazl Allami (1556—1602)," 276–77.

⁶⁰ Usmani, 277.

⁶¹ Usmani, 278.

⁶² Rizvi, *Religious and Intellectual History of the Muslims in Akbar's Reign, with Special Reference to Abu'l Fazl, 1556-1605*, 356.

⁶³ R. P. Tripathi, *Some Aspects of Muslim Administration* (Central Book Depot, 1966), 118.

being of his people over strict adherence to religious law when necessary.⁶⁴ Abul Fazl's theory of kingship and the Muslim concept of Khilafat have both similarities and differences. Abul Fazl replaces the Muslim religious law with divine will, which he believes is understood through the intuition of kings. While the Khilafat follows the law from the Quran, Hadith, and other sources, Abul Fazl believes in the law as interpreted by a wise king.

Both theories agree that a ruler has a higher mission, including religious and moral responsibilities, and that success is measured by fulfilling these duties. They both emphasize qualities like justice, benevolence, fear of God, and the well-being of the people. Both ideas are influenced by religious and moral thinking.⁶⁵ However, the differences are significant. The Khilafat is democratic, meaning the Khalifa (leader) is chosen by the Muslim community. In contrast, Abul Fazl's theory is autocratic, meaning the king's authority comes from divine will and his own greatness. The Khalifa's goal is to spread Islam, while Abul Fazl's king aims to maintain peace and harmony among different religions. Despite this, neither system is religiously neutral. The Khalifa maintains a clear distinction between Muslims and non-Muslims, while Abul Fazl's king treats them equally in terms of political rights and state matters. The Khalifa leads an active, mission-driven community, while the king leads a political society with some mystical elements and a slight missionary tendency.⁶⁶

Sulh-i Kul was a great contribution of Abul Fazl to Indian political thought.⁶⁷ This idea was not entirely novel, as both Buddhism and Hinduism have had their own idea of tolerance, and it also holds an important place in Islam, followed by Sufis.⁶⁸ Abul Fazl actually believed that social harmony, political stability, and national unity were impossible without the emotional integration of all the segments of Indian society. To support this doctrine, he emphasized the importance of the state and royalty. The king, acting like a benevolent and affectionate father, would not discriminate on any basis and would ensure the welfare of everyone. He believed that divine mercy extends to all forms of belief, and one should strive to embrace the principle of 'peace with all.' This principle of *Sulh-i Kul* became central to the Mughal rule in India, helping to sustain it for two and a half centuries. Although some conservative *Ulama* disapproved of it, *Sulh-i Kul* became a fundamental principle of the Mughal Empire. Even though Jehangir, Akbar's successor, annulled some of his father's religious innovations, he maintained and respected the policy of *Sulh-i Kul* and the political system based on it.⁶⁹ Abul Fazl argues that the rise of Akbar is a historical epoch he holds both spiritual and temporal powers he is the Lord of the age and he is the perfect man. Hence, he holds universal sovereignty.⁷⁰

Abul Fazl believes that the conquests in, Orissa, Bihar, and Bengal by Akbar show that the well-being of ordinary people depends on having one rule, one ruler, one guide, one aim, and one thought.⁷¹ He has also emphasized the importance of strong and capable military for firm rule. In

⁶⁴ Rizvi, *Religious and Intellectual History of the Muslims in Akbar's Reign, with Special Reference to Abu'l Fazl, 1556-1605*, 356.

⁶⁵ Tripathi, *Some Aspects of Muslim Administration*, 138–39.

⁶⁶ Tripathi, 138–39.

⁶⁷ Faruqui, *The Princes of the Mughal Empire, 1504–1719*, 145.

⁶⁸ Usmani, "Political Ideas of Shaikh Abul Fazl Allami (1556—1602)," 278.

⁶⁹ Usmani, 277–78.

⁷⁰ Rizvi, *Religious and Intellectual History of the Muslims in Akbar's Reign, with Special Reference to Abu'l Fazl, 1556-1605*, 360.

⁷¹ Rizvi, 360.

this regard he has provided a comprehensive set of instructions on how to build and maintain effective military force.⁷² Details about the divisions of army, equipment and war animals is also given.

CONCLUSION

It is clear that religion heavily influenced the entire medieval period. Social, political, and economic life during this time was deeply shaped by religious beliefs. Whether it was Hinduism, Buddhism, Zoroastrianism, or Islam all had a deep impact on the political thought and structure of government. Ideas of kingship and rule emanating from the Persian empire in time and space had also both practical and ideological impacts. The challenges before the rulers were manifold and diverse as well. They had to found, establish, consolidate, and protect their vast empire in a diverse society. An effective long-term rule cannot be only established through permanent military struggle and coercion. Hence it was very much a practical necessity for the rulers to develop and adopt that kind of political philosophy and political system that best suits their real requirements. This significant role was played by thinkers, philosophers, and top state officials present at the court at that time.

Abul Fazl and Ziauddin Barani were both influential political thinkers, each with distinct views on social stability and the ideal state. Abul Fazl, from the Mughal era, promoted secularism and believed the king should not rely on religion for rule, influenced by the diverse culture of his time, Persian political tradition, and practical necessity. For him, the king had absolute authority and he was a divine sovereign. He was, above all, religious authority. He was in essence himself the practical manifestation of God on earth. Emperor Akbar was his ideal perfect sovereign. He will reincarnate to remain the divine and universal sovereign.⁷³ When discussing the "ideal king," Abul Fazl envisioned a utopian ruler who was the "light of God," directly connected to divine wisdom, ensuring justice and unity among all people. For him, the king was above *sharia* law. The king had both temporal and spiritual authority. Kingship was also a divine blessing that could not be acquired by anyone through hard work. There was no question of revolt or rebellion against such a divine and just king. He was in essence the provider of comfort, peace, and progress to all of his subjects regardless of their religion. Therefore, it was the divine duty of all the people to obey and submit to the authority of the king without any question. We see a clear shift in the political thought of Abul Fazl during the Mughal era from the sultanate period. The shift is towards a more secular and Persian theory of kingship. But one significant thing is common. That is the king is the central authority. And all the political ideas are actually driven by the practical needs of the time. The situation within the Indian empire and the political, social, military, and religious situation changing, developing, and threatening this Indian empire from Central Asia, Afghanistan, Iran, and beyond. These ideas, forces, and challenges from within and without led to the development of the political ideas of Abul Fazl.

In contrast, Barani, from the Delhi Sultanate, insisted on the supremacy of Islam and the Quran, advocating a religious basis for the governance and authority of the king. Barani's ideal king was bound by conflicting virtues and justice based on *sharia*, advising the sultan to adopt any means to maintain the state while avoiding falsehood and injustice. The ideal king for Barani was Sultan

⁷² Blochmann, *Ain-i-Akbari Vol. 1*, 109–40.

⁷³ Beveridge, *The Akbarnama Of Abul Fazl Vol. 1*, 16.

Mahmud. Who was a true believer. On sovereignty, Barani, held conservative views, suppressing those against the nobility, including low-born individuals and Hindus, even banning their education. Barani believed that the foundation of governance should be firmly rooted in Islam and the principles of *Sharia*. He argued that the legitimacy of the sultanate depended on its adherence to Islamic principles, and the ruler should act as the protector and enforcer of the faith. Barani viewed the Sultan as the ultimate authority, divinely sanctioned to rule. However, the Sultan was not an absolute monarch but rather bound by *Sharia*. He was responsible for maintaining justice, ensuring the welfare of his subjects, and upholding Islamic morals and values. Barani had conservative views on the social hierarchy. He believed in maintaining a strict social order where the nobility and the ruling class held a privileged position. He was critical of the inclusion of low-born individuals and non-Muslims, especially Hindus, in positions of power. He is also opposed to any kind of revolt or rebellion against the sultan. However, he binds the sultan to follow *sharia* otherwise he will see the wrath of Allah in this world and hereafter.

Barani is also driven by the practical political needs of his time in formulating his ideas. The king is at the core of both Barani and Abul Fazl. Barani gives all authority to the sultan emanating from Islamic principles and Fazl gives all authority to the king by following the Persian theory of kingship and merging it with his own ideas. Both agree on the meritocratic structure of the administration of the empire for stability and progress. Both are of the opinion that a strong military is imperative for stable rule. Both believe that rulers must appoint qualified people for all important jobs in the empire. Barani gives preference to Muslims only and Fazl supports that everyone should be inducted just on qualification and ability not based on religion. Thus, at the important level of statecraft, both thinkers have splendid and expert understanding.

Both are conscious of the significance of the economy, markets, taxes, agriculture, administration, military, peace, stability, and overall proper organization of the empire. Abul Fazl's ideas are more complex and multifaceted whereas Barani's ideas are simpler having a single base. Abul Fazl seems to attribute divine characteristics and supernatural powers directly to his king. Barani on the other hand does give supreme authority and blessings of God to his sultan but his sultan is not a divine figure have some kind of supernatural powers. By looking at the ideas of both Barani and Abul Fazl we see a transition and change in the political thought during medieval India. This can be attributed to the practical needs of the time and also growing Persian influence and rising Hindu power that needed to be wooed.

Competing Interests

The author declared no known competing interests.

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